

A Literature Review on Training and Development Effectiveness and Managerial Implications

Bharat Kumar Lakra

Assistant Professor,
Deptt.of Industrial Relations &
Personnel Management,
Berhampur University,
Berhampur, Odisha

Abstract

Training and development as a developmental function has a direct impact on employees' performance and organisational effectiveness. Training and development play a pivotal role in the effectiveness of the organisation as it is most pervasive tools for increasing the individual performance as well as team performance to achieve organisational goals.

This paper seeks to critically examine the study a literature reviews has been done on different aspects of training and development. It covers various aspects of independents and dependents factors which influence the training and development, importance, organisational effectiveness and managerial implication.

The findings of this study suggest various factors which influences training and development effectiveness such as individual characteristics i.e., abilities, attitudes, self-efficacy, personality, demographics, experience, organisational characteristics i.e., organisational climate ,trainee selection, purpose, job characteristics, trainee expectation i.e., degree of interactions, focus of contents, program characteristics i.e., training need analysis, training methods, trainer abilities, training and development effectiveness i.e., training relevance, learning, job performance, results or organisational effectiveness etc.

Keywords: Training and Development, Effectiveness, Demographic Characteristics, Organisational Climate.

Introduction

Human resource consider as the most important assets of the any organisation. In this cut-throats completions today modern organisation are giving emphasis on the development of human resources which is the key factor for achieving organisational success and survival. Training and development as a HRD functions concerns with setting the performance of individual and groups for improving performance which contributes immensely to the development of employees as well as growth of the organisation. Training and development is the process of helping employees to acquire competencies in continuous and planned manner. Employees need competencies (knowledge, attitudes, values and skills) to perform tasks. Measuring the effectiveness of training and development in the organisation in terms of contributions or results is a matter of great concern for the top level of management or human resource development department in any organisation. Training and development programs should be design to solve the organisational performance based problems and to fill the gaps of employee's performance. T&D should make things happens and bring changes in the performance of the employees and that would enhance organisational effectiveness. Therefore, training and development has become most important HRD intervention to maintain a viable and knowledgeable workforce in the organisation.

Objectives of the Study

1. To review the existing literatures for improving conceptual clarity of training and development.
2. To examine the existing evidence that addresses the objectives, importance, transfers of training and development.
3. To critically review the different methodological approaches that researchers used in evaluating training and development effectiveness.
4. To provides a review of training and development literature focusing on the benefits for individuals, teams and organisation.

5. To reviews the contributions to understanding of factors in organisation and interprets the implications for training and development.

Review of Literature

Objectives of Training and Development Effectiveness

For the development of human asset, training and development becomes the base. Training and Development is a tool to attain individual, organisational needs related to the jobs undertaken and is also intended to improve the work culture of the group involved in a group task. Training needs for supervisions need to be identified through careful observations which indicate poor performance, low production, high cost, poor product quality, high scrap, spoilage, wastage, accidents, absenteeism and turnover (Sundaram, 1970). However, most of the training and development improves the self-confidence, motivation, identification with management goals, communication ability and skills (Banerji, 1981). A shift from knowledge to attitude is the main objective of training and development and identifies three areas of training: technical, skills and knowledge. He suggests that the emphasis on these three must vary according to the levels of employees (Bhatia, 1981). The immediate objectives of training should be to help the participants perform more effectively the activities enrolls they are performing at presents. The training programmes for branch manager should be design around the specific skills required by them (Bhatnagar, 1983). Management the real objectives views that while embarking upon a management programme, the real objective must be to focus on the individual manager, not the position in the company. The author's discussion on training needs analysis about the core competencies, job profiling and identification of competencies gaps – either against core competencies for individuals or against job profiles for generic roles is worth mentioning (Rechards, 1979). Training is a systematic modification of behaviour through learning; which occurs as a result of education, instruction, development and planned experiences. Training needs exist when there is a gap between the present performance of employee or group of employees and desired performance. Training is a systematic modification of behaviour through learning; which occurs as a result of education, instruction, development and planned experiences. Training needs exist when there is a gap between the present performance of employee or group of employees and desired performance. (Andrews, 2003). To maintain a competitive advantage, organisation must succeed in three domains: Finance, products or market and human capital. Worldwide economic cycles tend to create conditions in which obtaining sufficient finance is either equally easy or equally difficult for most of the organisations of the same size. More important, in today's global economy, all managers can sell to the same market share and the product development cycles are such that differences in product innovation are much smaller than in year past. Thus, it is the third domain – building and maintaining a more capable and better trained workforce- that may offer

the most sustainable advantage available to most organisations.

Importance of Training and development Effectiveness

Role of training in developing human resources is another work of relevance. The authors concluded that an organisation should have well-defined training policy as well as training manual and training should be made an ongoing process. Regarding the executive development programmes the authors have concluded that these programmes have been found to be useful in improving the productivity, efficiency and effectiveness of managers. The authors have also suggested that these programmes should be included as an integral part of training programme (Badhu & Saxena, 1999). However, training and development best process is probably need assessment. Therefore, training need assessment is the foundation of the entire instructional design process. It establishes the content of subsequent training. If not done correctly, or at all, the job-relatedness, effectiveness and validity of any training programme is jeopardized. In addition, needs assessment provides a database support or justify resource allocation for other human resource functions (Goldstein, 2001). Effective practices by organisations related to staffing and training were positively related to perceived organisational performance (Delaney & Huselid, 1996). Training and development is the key component in the building and maintaining an effective employee workforce, which in turn drives metrics of corporate well-being (Aguinis & Kraiger, 2009). Training and development is not limited to building individual skills- training can be used to improve teams as well. Sometimes this training is designed to provide individuals with skills they can apply when working with any group of teammates. A meta-analysis conducted to examine the effectiveness of management training across six content areas (general management, human relationship/ leadership, self-awareness, problem solving/ decision making, training and motivation/values), seven training methods (lecture, group decision, leader match, sensitivity training, behaviour modelling, group discussion with role playing or practice and multiple methods) and four outcome criteria (subjective learning, objective learning, subjective behaviour and objective results) and reported a positive effort for training among nearly all combinations of content, methods and outcome (Burke & Day, 1986). Training strategy does four things; first, it conveys information to the trainees (i.e., the concepts, facts and information they need to learn). Second, it demonstrates the desired behaviour, cognition and attitudes; third, it creates opportunity to practice the KSAs to be learned. Fourth, it gives the feedback to the trainee on how he she is doing with respect to the learning and as a result, it allows for remediation. Most training programs that attempt to build skills should have all these components present (Salas, Cannon, & Bowers, 2001).

Transfer of Training and Development Effectiveness

Transfer of training refers to the degree to which trainees effectively apply the knowledge, skills and attitudes gained in a training context to the job. Transfer of training model describes the transfer of training process. The authors depicted those interactions among training design characteristic, trainee characteristics, and the work environment in explaining learning and transfer. The factors in the work environment include supervisory and peer supports as well as opportunity to perform learned behaviours on the job (Baldwin & Ford, 1988). Successful training not only considers the elements that will influence training beforehand, but also examines facets within the transfer environment (Grossman & Salas, 2011). In general training transfer is the ability to utilise all Knowledge, experiences, skills and behaviour learned during at the workplace. Training Transfer is considered successful if the training program increases the trainees' performance while assuming that the training is related to their work. Transfer is facilitating by both a supportive climate and aspects of the experiences, skills and behaviour learned during at the workplace. Training Transfer is considered successful if the training program increases the trainees' performance while assuming that the training is related to their work. Transfer is facilitate by both a supportive climate and aspects of the work environment, specially, environments characterised by socio-technical system design factors like high job involvement and information sharing, job design variables such as task autonomy and organisational commitment to quality (Kontoghiorghes, 2004). Designing and selecting the appropriate strategy is a key to maximise transfer of training. The organisational context after training can have as a great an impact on training effectiveness as what happens during training because post training events influences whether trained skills transfer and are used on the job. As noted (Rouiller & Goldstein, 1993), introduced the construct of transfer climate, showing that the extent to which trainees perceive the post training environment (including the supervision) as supportive of the skills covered in training had a significant effect on whether those skills are practiced and maintained. (Tracey, Tannenbaum, & Kavangh, 1995) Conducted an important study for clarifying the impact of the post training climate environment (i, e., the transfer environment) – practically the role of supervisory support. They found that original climate and culture were directly related to post training outcomes. Positive climate and social support positively affect transfer. In other words a supportive post training environment affects employees mind set, which in turn will determine whether they use what they have learned in training. Learning transfer occurs when learning behaviours must be generalised to the job context and maintained over a period of time on the job. (Baldwin, Effects on Alternative Modeling Strategies on Outcomes of Interpersonal Skills and Training, 1992) in his research study pointed out that training design(principles of learning, training content, perception of training quality), work environment

(support on all levels, organisational climate) and trainees characteristics (personality, motivation) predict learning transfer. One organisational factors that has been largely overlooked as a potential contributor to training transfer theory is work place design. Yet elements of the physical environment have been a part of human resource development efforts for decades. (Baldwin & Ford, Transfer of Training: A Review and Directions for Future Research, 1988) Address in their study to include the physical environment as an emerging work environment factors imparting transfer. Their study posits that training outcomes and training inputs factors have both a direct and indirect efforts on conditions of transfer. Six linkages are critical to understand the transfer process. These linkage are: (6) Training outcomes of leaning and retention has a direct effect on the condition of transfer; (5,4) Trainee characteristics and wor4k environment characteristics are hypothesized to have a direct effect on transfer regardless of initial learning during the training programme or retention of training materials.(3,2&1) Training outcomes(learning and retention) are viewed as directly affected by the three training inputs of training design, trainee characteristics and work environment characteristics. The study by (Carolyn, 1997) took 45 technical staffs that participated in the interpersonal skills training program as sample and measured their reaction three times. Based on the first assessment, 86% of the staff informed that they can understand the training and could master the new knowledge and skills resulted from self awareness and self motivation. Later on, the researcher made follow up assessment a month after the trainee competed the training. Finding shows that almost half or 49% of the trainees had successfully transferred their training to their workplaces. This finding is very important since trainees are able to internalise the knowledge and able to use them at the working place. It is obvious that the success factors for the transfer of training are the motivation factors aside from the similarity of the training environment and work environment. (Wagner & Campell, 1994). In their study raises the question whether skills learned from the external program initiatives can be transferred to the actual workplace even through external programmes are a popular techniques used to train managers that handling training programmes directly. This study found that the external programmes offer new training content and have the tendency to resolve conflicts at workplace. Interpersonal skills leaned in the programmes can be applied to the working places. At the same time, this study brought a new idea that represents external training programme or reality training. Reality training refers to resemble the trainees work environment and this will help to speed up the transfer of training process to the work places. Transfer of training does not rely on only exclusive factors. It does not evolve naturally but need constant work, planned improvements, accurate and effective strategies.

Evaluation of Training and Development Effectiveness

Evaluation is part of an effective training and development system. Evaluation allows organisation to continue conducting training and development programme that works and modify or discontinue training and development that does not work.

Training and development evaluation refers to answer the systematic collection of data in order to answer the questions of whether learning objectives were achieved and /or whether accomplishment of those objectives resulted in enhanced performance on the job. (Virmani & Seth, 1985), In their book depicted that evaluating management trainee and development includes evaluation of training context, input evaluation, Post-training evaluation, transfer of learning and job improvement. The study suggested for job evaluation as a follow-up after six months to one year. All these aspects have been evaluated for the executive training programme organised in the administrative staff college, Hyderabad, which brings out the impact of institutional programmes. Evaluating training, instead of just studying the reactions of the trainees, the study could be carried out in four different levels viz., i.e., reaction, Learning, behaviour and results. On each level of evaluation of training are important. (De Meuse, Hostager, & Neill, 2007) In their study presented the dimensions for evaluating the efficacy of training programmes namely emotional and behavioural reactions, judgments (leaning), Personal consequences (Behavioural change) and organisational outcomes on the basis of Kirkpatrick's model of training evaluation. It also indicates that the appropriate evaluation can be done by comparing the pre-training expectations with post-training results by carrying out the survey. (Kraiger, 2002) In his research study emphasised that learning is multidimensional (including affective, behavioural and cognitive components). Thus, the question of whether instructional objectives were achieved usually requires multiple measures of different types of outcomes, for example, measures of changes in declarative knowledge (whether trainees now know more), in skilled behaviour (whether trainees are doing things better), and in self-efficacy for transfer (whether there has been a positive affective change).

Specifying evaluation criteria is straight forward. Following a TNA, the primary training needs are used to identify both instructional objectives and training outcomes; Broad training and development outcomes may be translated into evaluation measures in several ways. Historically, organisations and researchers have relied on (Kirkpatrick's 1994, Evaluating Training Programmes: The Four Levels) hierarchy as a framework for evaluating training programmes. In late 1950s Kirkpatrick responded to request from practitioners for useful techniques for evaluating training programmes by recommending four 'levels' by which training programs may be evaluated. Kirkpatrick recommended measuring in sequence, trainees 'reactions' (how well trainee linked the training), learning (principles, facts, or skilled learned), behaviour (resulting changes in behaviour on the job) and result (tangible outcomes of training

such as more profit or fewer errors). American Society for Training and development in 2010 reported that Kirkpatrick's framework remains the basis for much of the evaluation efforts in organisation today. This is evident in the yearly surveys of the organisation's training practices conducted by the American Society of Training and Development (ASTD). Since the late 1960s, ASTD has surveyed a sample of the organisations regarding their training practices, giving a snapshot of what organizations actually do with respect to training investments, training delivery and evaluation. Evaluation practices have always been and continue to be tracked in terms of the "four levels". Today, over 90% of companies surveyed measured trainee reactions, over 80% measured trainee learning, and over 50% measured on-the-job behaviour and nearly 40% reported measuring results.

The effectiveness of any training and development programme is not evaluated based on the participant's performance while attending the training alone but the application of knowledge and the skills learned during the training programme to the work place. A Training and Development Programme is considered effective if it can change the attitude or behaviour of the trainees when they come back to work. Therefore, the internalisation of knowledge and skills are considered successful when it can be applied at workplace effectively. The training effectiveness is dependent on two considerations (i) Trainers are fully responsible for training and if employees do not show results, the trainer should be held responsible (ii) Training effectiveness depends on the kind of atmosphere and the culture that is prevalent back at home (Mehta, 1970). Whether demographic variables have any role to play in influencing the effectiveness of the training programme. A comparative study of difference between pre-training and post-training results to find out the effectiveness of the training programme was also done. It also revealed that the most of the important factors in explaining the effectiveness of training programme. The measures used to study are skills and knowledge gained, trainee reactions to the training course, perceived usefulness of the training course and the trainee efforts to gain skills and knowledge (Ibrahim, 2003). The conditions that maximise training performance were different than those that maximised transfer or ensure long-term retention of training learning. The strategies require transfer appropriate processing; or cognitions the trainees must engage into apply their training in the transfer environment, generalisation and maintenance of skills enhanced. Such strategies make performance in training more challenging and viable; however trainees learn understanding rules and principles more deeply as a result (Suhmidt & Bjoke, 1992). Training success is determined not only by the quality of training (or effectiveness of a specific method), but by interpersonal, social and structural characteristics reflecting the relationship of the trainee and the training programme to the broader organisational context. Variables such as organisational support or an individual's readiness for

training could augment or negate the direct impact of the training itself (Noe, 1986).

Learning during training is influenced by factors both prior to and during the training itself. Generally, pre-training influences may be categorised as organisational level, social or team level, or individual level influences. Examples of organisational level pertaining influences include perceived organisational support for training and whether training is mandatory or optional. Trainees consistent with organisational goals supported by top management and required of all members.

An important social influence is the superior, who can positively or negatively influence trainees' motivation for training or their perceptions of the utility of the training. Supervisor can positively influence training outcomes by referring positively to the training process, by clarifying probable learning outcomes or how those outcomes will be advantageous to job performance or future development and by providing interpersonal and technical support to trainees prior to and during training. Peers or co-workers can exert a similar social impact on trainees.

Individual level variables refer to trainees' readiness for training as well as their course specific motivation to learn. Readiness for training is a general state of preparedness for training: trainees should have sufficient cognitive ability to learn the material; they should have sufficient understanding of their jobs to see how the tasks, knowledge and skills covered in training are relevant to the job; and they should be relatively free from anxieties and fears about the learning environment (Noe & Coquitt, Planning for Training Impact: Principles of Training Effectiveness, 2002).

Training effectiveness model present that individual characteristics including trainability, personality, age and attitudes influence training motivation; and in turn, learning during training ;and later, the transfer of training and job performance. Other attitudes such as self-efficacy, valence, job involvement, organisational commitment and career exploration have been shown to be related to training motivation as well (Colquitt, LePine, & Noe, 2000).

Measuring training and development effectiveness is a very cumbersome task and it requires utmost care in evaluating the programs. It brings out the outcome and worth of the program. The lots of model has been developed on training and development effectiveness but Kirkpatrick (1976) being the pioneer who explained the four level method of training evaluation criteria. This model delineates four levels of training outcomes: reaction, learning, behaviour, and results. Level-1: includes evaluation of reactions on the training program. Kirkpatrick (1959) originally discussed reactions in terms of how well participants linked a particular program. In practice, it evaluates trainees' affective and attitudinal response and feeling to the quality (e. g. Satisfaction with the instructor or the relevance (e. g. Work-related utility) of training. Level-2: Learning Criteria, it evaluates the extent to which trainees have acquired knowledge and skills during the course of the training. It brings out the outcome of training programs that affects on

trainees. Level-3: Behaviour Criteria, it evaluates the extent to which trainees have applied on the job in terms of their behaviour or performance or result following a training program. Level-4: Results Criteria, it evaluates the extent to which the training program has enhanced departmental or organisational outcomes such as sales and profit and it typically focus on financial measures which measures about the impact of the training effectiveness. Training motivation along with Kirkpatrick model's of evaluation is important as trainees will be more motivated to perform well in training if the perceived that (1) high effort will lead to high performance in training, (2) high performance in training will lead to high job performance and (3) high job performance is instrumental in obtaining desired outcomes (Noe R. A., 1986) .This model is base on about motivation because motivation itself an immense factor which affects the performance as well as training outcome. CIPP Evaluation model of programme evaluation developed by Daniel L. Stufflebeam (1983).It refers to the four phases of evaluation: Context evaluation, Input evaluation, Process evaluation and Product evaluation. It is based upon the view that the most important purpose of evaluation is to improve the functioning of the programme. (1) Context evaluation includes training and development need analysis and formulating objectives in the light of these needs. (2)Input evaluation includes an assessment of content of the programme. It is plan, design and developed to examine the extent to which programme policies, procedures and methods support the goals of the programs or not. An input evaluation is an assessment of the action plan of the programs. It involves evaluation policies, procedures, schedules, administration and budgets for organising programs. (3)Process evaluation includes the programme implementation aspect. It is an ongoing and systematic monitoring of the programme. (4)Product evaluation includes assessment of predetermined objectives of the programmes are achieved or not and judging the improvement of organisation short- term and long-term goals.

Jack Phillip's Return on Investment (ROI) Evaluation Model suggested in 1996. Phillip's framework provides trainers a logical framework to view ROI both from human resource performance and business outcomes perspectives. He suggested adding another level to Kirkpatrick four level evaluation approaches to calculate the return on investment. This approach translates the worth of the training into monetary value which effect address on ROI. Since Kirkpatrick established his original model, other theorist and indeed Kirkpatrick himself, have referred to fifth level, namely ROI.

CIRO Evaluation Model was proposed in 1970 by Warr, Birds & Rackson. This model is based on the evaluation of four aspects of training: context, input, reaction and outcome. Context evaluation focuses on factors such as training need identification and setting of objectives in relation to the organisation's culture and climate. Input evaluation focuses on design and delivery of training programmes. Reaction evaluation focuses on gaining

and using information about the quality of training experiences. Outcome evaluation focus on the achievement gained from the activities and assessed at three levels: immediate, intermediate and ultimate evaluation. Immediate evaluation attempts to measure changes in knowledge, skills and attitude before a trainee return to the job. Immediate evaluation refers to the impact of training on the job performance and how learning is transferred back to workplace. Ultimate evaluation attempts to assess the impact of training on departmental or organisational performance in terms of overall results.

The research have evaluated training and development effectiveness using various measurement dimensions and criteria including reaction (satisfaction), knowledge acquired (learning performance), knowledge applications (training transfer) and costs and benefits (organisational performance) simultaneously to determine the training effectiveness.

In summary, previous studies on training and development effectiveness seems to comprises four dimensions which can be considered together to determine the status of training effectiveness. These include satisfaction, learning performance, individual performance and organisational performance.

Challenges of Training and Development Effectiveness

Organisations are facing pressing challenges and opportunities for training and development. For example , a few common trends include dealing with cross-cultural workforce; the retraining of displaced personnel, a new generation entering the workforce with different motivations, expectations and approaches to learning; access to rapidly emerging technologies that can accelerate or distract from employee development and need to develop an adaptive, flexible workforce that can adjust to changes, while simultaneously ensuring that employees have the specific skills they need to do today's work. At the organisation level, companies need employees who are both ready to perform today's jobs and able to learn and adjust to changing demands. For employees, that involves developing both job-specific and for companies it means taking actions to ensure that employees are motivated to learn. Organisations strive for efficiency and seek competitive advantage. As noted that well-designed training and development programme can enable employees to be more productive and higher performers and hence worthy for higher pay. It is important to understand how best to use training and development helps a company establish a skilled and competitive talent pool.

Managerial Implications

Training and development helps in constructive development for the organisation as well as improving the employee's behaviour and attitudes towards the jobs. It is very important for an organisation to compete with this challenging and changing world. This study helps organisation to understand the importance of training and development. It will also help organisation to understand which factors are important to keep in

mind while plan and implement the training and development programs. This paper reports the findings of different literature reviews which cover many aspects of training and development like individual factor variables of participants, training expectation, motivation, expectation fulfilment and training effectiveness. This is the most popular and commonly used evaluation model in organisations. In order to gain comprehensive insight, it is advisable that organisations must do the evaluation using all levels. This is particularly so when investment on training and development is substantial. This also increases the accountability of training functions and training administrators significantly apart from providing valuable data for improving the training management. HR managers and trainers must adapt it in organisations, as this is the most comprehensive training and development evaluation model available to practitioners.

The organisations spend substantial amount of money, energy and time on training and development of the employees. Training and development is one function that receives overwhelming attention in all types of organisation. Therefore, it is also essential for companies to accrue the proportionate benefits.

Conclusion

This research study gives deep insight to the review of literature on training and development and its effectiveness to organisation. The researcher has gone through the research articles published by the researcher on the training and development and analysed the factors influencing the training and development effectiveness. The study revealed that various factors influence the training and development effectiveness but four factors i.e. Individual characteristics, organisational characteristics, program characteristics, objectives, and transfer of training and development revealed to be stronger and more responsible for effective training and development. So top management should ensure all factors are well taken care for actions plan to improve the effectiveness of the training and development.

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